

Color bands polymer in methacrylic acid polymerization[†]

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White and pink alternative color band polymers were prepared by frontal polymerization technique in methacrylic acid-methanol, -ethanol, -butanol systems in presence of benzoyl peroxide, hydroquinone and *N,N*-dimethylaniline in a glass tube at 30°. The front velocity and frequency were found to be dependent on the initial concentration of methanol/ethanol/butanol, benzoyl peroxide and hydroquinone. A tentative mechanism of color band formation was proposed.

The innovative technique of frontal polymerization was first discovered in 1967 in the former Soviet Union at the Institute of Chemical Physics at Chernogolovka (Russia) where Merzhanov and Borovinskaya¹ discovered the process of self-propagating high temperature synthesis to prepare technologically useful ceramics and intermetallic compounds. A compressed pellet of reactants was ignited at one end and this resulted in a self-propagating combustion wave. The method had the advantage that the initial stimulus was the only energy input required and that superior materials were produced. In 1972, Chechilo and Enikolopyan applied the same approach to the free-radical polymerization of vinyl monomers. Using a steel reactor under high pressure (>3000 atm) they studied descending fronts of methyl methacrylate using peroxide initiator^{2,3}. In 1991, Pojman rediscovered this phenomenon at ambient pressure in standard test tube⁴. An isothermal mode also exists, often referred to as 'interfacial gel polymerization' studies first in Japan by Koike *et al.*⁵ and more recently in Russia⁶. They produced some commercially useful materials with gradients of refractive index⁷. Srivastava *et al.*⁸ synthesized polyacrylic acid in acrylic acid/benzoyl peroxide/*N,N*-dimethylaniline system in glass tube at ambient temperature and pressure using frontal polymerization technique.

Recently, Srivastava *et al.*⁹ have used the technique of frontal polymerization to prepare new kind of polymeric material, white and pink band colored solid machinable polymer in methacrylic acid/benzoyl peroxide/methanol/*N,N*-dimethylaniline system at ambient temperature and pressure in a glass tube. They have also studied the dependence of banded color structure on the initial concentration of methanol and benzoyl peroxide. Synthesis of novel machinable solid alternate white and pink color banded poly-

mer by an unusual method of frontal polymerization⁹ without solvent is of vital importance for science and technology. It is a mode of converting monomer into polymer by means of localized reaction zone that propagates by coupling of thermal diffusion and the heat released by the reaction; such a front can exist with a free radial polymerization.

In this communication, we report white and pink colored polymer in methacrylic acid/benzoyl peroxide/hydroquinone/*N,N*-dimethylaniline with methanol, ethanol and butanol in a glass tube.

Results and discussion

Banded colored polymer have been synthesized by frontal polymerization technique in a number of systems, methacrylic acid/benzoyl peroxide/methanol or ethanol or butanol/hydroquinone/*N,N*-dimethylaniline, in a glass tube at 30° temperature and one atmosphere pressure. The frontal polymerization will ultimately have three benefits over traditional methods of polymer synthesis: reduced energy cost, reduced waste production and the ability to produce unique morphologies. A desirable feature of frontal polymerization is the rapid and uniform conversion of monomer to polymer. This can be advantageous because of the heat of reaction is used to increase the rate of reaction. Also, the absence of solvent eliminates the need for polymer-solvent separation, which requires energy and can have detrimental environmental ramifications:

This banded structure occurs in a concentration range of methacrylic acid, benzoyl peroxide, hydroquinone, alcohol and temperature range. Color bands of (a) methanol system, (b) ethanol system and (c) butanol system are shown in Fig. 1. A typical plot of front velocity against time of butanol system is shown in Fig. 2.

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

Fig. 1. Photographs of stationary white and pink bands.

(a) Methanol system : [Methacrylic acid] = 9.52 M, [Benzoyl peroxide] = 0.017 M, [Methanol] = 3.12 M, [Hydroquinone] = 3.9×10^{-5} M, [N,N-DMA] = 25 mg, tube dia. (i) = 13 mm, length = 80 mm, temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

(b) Ethanol system : [Methacrylic acid] = 8.26 M, [Benzoyl peroxide] = 0.031 M, [Ethanol] = 1.72 M, [Hydroquinone] = 6.81×10^{-4} M, [N,N-DMA] = 25 mg, tube dia. (i) = 10 mm, length = 80 mm, temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

(c) Butanol system : [Methacrylic acid] = 9.97 M, [Benzoyl peroxide] = 0.0619 M, [Butanol] = 1.0928 M, [N,N-DMA] = 25 mg, [Hydroquinone] = 4.54×10^{-4} M, tube dia. (i) = 10 mm, length = 80 mm, temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Fig. 2. Front position against time of butanol system; [Methacrylic acid] = 9.97 M, [Benzoyl peroxide] = 0.0619 M, [Butanol] = 1.0928 M, [N,N-DMA] = 25 mg, [Hydroquinone] = 4.54×10^{-4} M, tube dia. (i) = 10 mm, length = 80 mm, temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$: (a) [Butanol] = 1.0923 M, (b) [Butanol] = 1.366 M, (c) [Butanol] = 1.639 M, (d) [Butanol] = 1.912 M, (e) [Butanol] = 2.185 M.

Effect of change of alcohol :

Color band appears in a range of methanol, ethanol and butanol concentration, a plot of front velocity against alcohol concentration is shown in Fig. 3. It is clear from the figure that front velocity decreases with increase in alcohol concentration. Front velocity appears to be higher in methanol system and decreases with increase in molecular weight of alcohol. The range of concentration in which the band appears decreases with increase in molecular weight of alcohol.

Effect of change of benzoyl peroxide concentration :

The effect of change of front velocity with benzoyl peroxide concentration is shown in Fig. 4. It is clear from the figure that the front velocity is higher in methanol system

Fig. 3. Front velocity as a function of alcohol concentration.

(a) Methanol system : [Methacrylic acid] = 9.52 M, [Benzoyl peroxide] = 0.017 M, [Hydroquinone] = 3.9×10^{-5} M, [N,N-DMA] = 25 mg, tube dia. (i) = 10 mm, length = 80 mm, temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

(b) Ethanol system : [Methacrylic acid] = 8.2638 M, [Benzoyl peroxide] = 0.03096 M, [Hydroquinone] = 6.81×10^{-4} M, [N,N-DMA] = 25 mg, tube dia. (i) = 10 mm, length = 80 mm, temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

(c) Butanol system : [Methacrylic acid] = 9.9733 M, [Benzoyl peroxide] = 0.06193 M, [Hydroquinone] = 4.54×10^{-4} M, [N,N-DMA] = 25 mg, tube dia. (i) = 10 mm, length = 80 mm, temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

and lowest in butanol system, and ethanol system shows the intermediate value. The ratio in which band appears increase with molecular weight of the alcohol.

Effect of change of hydroquinone concentration :

Effect of change of hydroquinone concentration on front velocity is shown in Fig. 5. In general, front velocity increases with increase in the hydroquinone concentration. It has got a limit between which band appears. Beyond the lower limit front appears without band, on the other hand, at the upper limit front does not appear. The rate of increase of front velocity decreases with increase of molecular weight of alcohol.

Mechanism of color band :

The reaction mixture containing methacrylic acid, benzoyl peroxide, N,N-dimethylaniline under ambient condition and also at elevated temperature shows front but does not develop any band or color. When the reaction mixture contains alcohol front and band appear but does not develop any color. On the other hand, when the reaction mixture contains hydroquinone in adequate concentration color band appears. In absence of hydroquinone, front and white band appear but does not show any color band. This sequence of reaction shows that color band appears due to

Fig. 4. Front velocity as a function of benzoyl peroxide (BP) concentration.

- (a) Methanol system : [Methacrylic acid] = 9.52 M, [Methanol] = 3.49 M, [Hydroquinone] = 3.9×10^{-5} M, [N,N-DMA] = 0.29 mg, tube dia. (i) = 13 mm, length = 80 mm, temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.
 (b) Ethanol system : [Methacrylic acid] = 8.2638 M, [Ethanol] = 1.7148 M, [Hydroquinone] = 4.54×10^{-4} M, [N,N-DMA] = 25 mg, tube dia. (i) = 10 mm, length = 80 mm, temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.
 (c) Butanol system : [Methacrylic acid] = 9.9733 M, [Butanol] = 1.0928 M, [Hydroquinone] = 4.54×10^{-4} M, [N,N-DMA] = 25 mg, tube dia. (i) = 10 mm, length = 80 mm, temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Fig. 5. Front velocity as a function hydroquinone (HQ) concentration.

- (a) Methanol system : [Methacrylic acid] = 9.52 M, [Benzoyl peroxide] = 0.017 M, [Methanol] = 3.49 M, [N,N-DMA] = 0.29 mg, tube dia. (i) = 13 mm, length = 80 mm, temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.
 (b) Ethanol system : [Methacrylic acid] = 8.2638 M, [Benzoyl peroxide] = 0.03096 M, [Ethanol] = 1.7148 M, [N,N-DMA] = 25 mg, tube dia. (i) = 10 mm, length = 80 mm, temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.
 (c) Butanol system : [Methacrylic acid] = 9.9733 M, [Benzoyl peroxide] = 0.06193 M, [Butanol] = 1.0928 M, [N,N-DMA] = 25 mg, tube dia. (i) = 10 mm, length = 80 mm, Temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

free radical and thermal oxidation and polymerization of methacrylic acid with hydroquinone in alcohol. The colored polymers thus formed have solubility in alcohol. Further investigations are under way to separate the color polymer and to identify it.

Experimental

Benzoyl peroxide (C.D.H.), methanol, ethanol and butanol (E. Merck) were used without further purification. Methacrylic acid (C.D.H.) was purified by fractional distillation and inhibitor was removed by conventional methods. The freshly prepared solutions were used each day. Solutions of benzoyl peroxide and hydroquinone were prepared by dissolving in methacrylic acid. The frontal polymerization was performed in a glass tube of 10 mm diameter and 8 cm height. The solution of benzoyl peroxide, hydroquinone, methacrylic acid, alcohol (methanol or ethanol or butanol) was taken in a glass tube. In the homogeneous reaction mixture, *N,N*-dimethylaniline was added from the top of the tube. After addition of *N,N*-dimethylaniline, nucleation started at the top of solution and attained the form of front within a few minutes. Front thus formed moved downward with a uniform velocity with the formation of colored bands. The front velocity was measured with the help of cathodometer.

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